

Challenges and opportunities in the HMI design for EV

Caterina Calefato^{1*}, Leandro Guidotti¹, Elisa Landini¹, Roberto Montanari¹, Francesco Tesauri¹

1. RE:Lab srl, Italy

* caterina.calefato@re-lab.it

Abstract

The 2050 scenario for transport decarbonisation includes vehicles that are likely to be more electrified than currently. Together with the GHG emissions, there is also the problem of congested European cities: the electric vehicles for L-category for daily urban commutes play an interesting role in the electrification of transport. The RESOLVE project aims at enabling the development of a range of cost-effective, energy-efficient and comfortable ELVs, to make them a reliable and attractive alternative to ICE vehicles. Since EVs driver copes with a range of new and unfamiliar technologies, it is vital for automotive manufacturers to make the driver's interaction experience positive and rewarding, and to gap the user lack of confidence and trust. A proper design of HMI that implements familiarity and continuity affordance can decisively support in overcoming these issues. This paper discusses a design strategy that includes continuity affordance for the HMI of EVs.

Keywords: Continuity affordance, Electric vehicles, HMI design

Introduction

The European Union undertook the objective to reduce its greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 80-95% compared to 1990 levels by 2050 [6] [18]. Of course an emission reduction of that extent will require considerable restructuring in all sectors of the energy system. The transport sector undergoes major changes in the decarbonisation scenario, which lead to 60% lower emissions in 2050 from 1990 levels and 70% lower emissions compared to the reference scenario for 2050. One of the main concern at this aim is the application of alternative propulsion systems and/or the use of alternative, less carbon-intensive energy, carriers and fuels. The 2050 scenario includes vehicles that are likely to be more electrified than currently, and use alternative energy carriers such as electricity and hydrogen. The pure electric powered transport holds the greatest potential for GHG emissions reductions, since electricity can be produced from essentially carbon-neutral sources. Nevertheless EU is working to introduce electric vehicles beyond 2020, improving technology over time and developing the recharging infrastructure [6].

Together with the GHG emissions, there is also the problem of more and more congested European cities, due to the increased demand and usage of motor vehicles of a growing urban population [8].

An interesting role in the electrification of transport is played by the electric vehicles for L-category¹ (ELVs). As it happens for the other electric vehicles, the rate of adoption of ELVs is not high enough to have a significant impact on the attainment of emission targets, or an improvement in urban living conditions [5]. One of the most significant challenges remain principally in the area of electrical energy storage, particularly in terms of cost, weight, volume, efficiency and power delivery. These limitations also impact on the useful range of electric vehicles compared to conventional equivalents [6]. Moreover models currently on the market do not provide a similar or superior experience to the driver in terms of comfort, handling, stability, or other user-related aspects [5]. The costs associated with these alternative vehicles are likely to be a barrier to a significant market penetration. The vehicles are likely to remain more expensive than traditional Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles. In this respect, it is important to note that much of the efficiency of an engine is related to the way it is used: this means that the improvement of the energy efficiency of vehicle will also reduce the costs of using the vehicle itself. Any option that improves the energy efficiency of vehicles will lead to less energy being required to travel the same distance, which, if everything else remains the same, will make vehicles cheaper to use [6]. Such a rebound effect underlines the importance of a coordinated approach to the implementation of complementary policy measures. Working towards that vision, RESOLVE project (www.resolve-project.eu) aims at enabling the development of a range of cost-effective, energy efficient and comfortable ELVs that will entice ICE car drivers to switch from cars to ELVs for their daily urban commutes. Since the HMI plays a crucial role in improving the user experience with a road vehicle, a tailored HMI design strategy has been designed and it will be applied in the next project steps.

The RESOLVE project

The RESOLVE project is an example of the new trend of the research in the automotive domain. The RESOLVE project, *Range of Electric SOLUTIONS for L-category Vehicles*, is a three years research project co-funded by the European Commission within the H2020 program, started the 1st May 2015. The RESOLVE consortium is made of a well-balanced and qualified group of 14 partners and it is optimally positioned to drive such technological advancements and bring them to the market: PIAGGIO and KTM, each developing one of the demonstrator vehicles, are the two largest LV producers in EU, while the complete ELV value chain is represented in the consortium and complemented by top component suppliers, research institutes, engineering companies and universities. The project is built on four pillars:

1. Powertrain cost reduction.
2. Total vehicle energy efficiency.
3. Improving driver experience.

¹ According to the European Regulation, a wide range of different vehicles are included in the “L-category”, each one being described in detail by the Reg.168/2013/EC “on the approval and market surveillance of two–or three–wheel vehicles and quadricycles” [10].

4. Handling and stability.

Improving the driver experience with ELVs through HMI

The EVs driver copes with a range of new and unfamiliar technologies and it will be vital for automotive manufacturers to make the driver's interaction experience positive and rewarding [19]. The drivers of electric vehicle will encounter completely new concepts such as range management, charging procedures, recharging duration, very low noise, strong acceleration and limited space etc. [3], in addition to unfamiliar issues such as novel start and stopping procedures and the effect that driving style has on the potential mileage range [19].

This obviously lead to deliver to user different information about energy than ICE vehicles such as the amount of electricity stored and expected mileage on current charge [7] [19] [21]. A crucial and critical ELV HMI issue is to provide drivers the energy-related information in a reliable and precise manner and to deal with different ways for displaying data in order to gap the user lack of confidence in estimated range and state of charge.

Driver should understand how to utilize the EV's special driving qualities and should be supported in developing trust and understanding which factors affect the available range, in order to be able to reduce concerns and range anxiety (i.e. tips on the proper use of the regenerative braking) [19].

Although EV field trials have a long-standing tradition [1] [16], there is very little published research about how to design an EV HMI in order to overcome these issues. More research is needed to understand which information and data should be included in the user interface as well as on how to present it. The HMI research shall start from answering the following questions [19]:

- What is the relevant information content that needs to be presented to the driver of an electric vehicle?
- How, i.e. in what form, should these information be presented?
- Can perception of information relevance be influenced?
- Can the information content be perceived as more or less useful depending on the way it is presented?
- Should the interface be traditional, i.e. similar to that of a conventional internal combustion engine vehicle, or not?
- Can the shift in technology be used to create a new, innovative kind of vehicle interface?
- How useful it would be to have remote access to certain types of information when away from the vehicle?

Answering to those questions drove the RESOLVE project towards the definition of a global HMI strategy that addresses the EVs design problems (that will be presented in next paragraphs). The strategy is global because it encompasses all functions defined within one's own design project, but it will allow designing and implementing specific HMI solutions for each foreseen application, taking into account the different vehicle architectures and therefore the different HMI requirements.

Familiarity and continuity affordance as design principles

In order to assure a rewarding driving experience both to inexperienced and experienced EV drivers that may cope with totally new functions, HMI must be designed taking care of the *familiarity* concept. The introduction of the concept of familiarity can drive the HMI design process toward the gain of the user positive attitude. The concept of familiarity captures the “cognitive and emotional processes through which drivers gain enough information about, understanding of, and emotional attachment to a technology” [20].

If electric vehicles are rife of “familiarity”, the totally new functions can seamlessly be integrated in the driver past experience because they are supported by proper HMI affordances. Past studies explain how affordances derived from well-known and widely used technology encourage a more proactive use of new technology [4]. In this case, affordance stands for the elements mainly embodied in the user interfaces, which suggests how a technology may be interacted with [12] [15]. Moreover, the *continuity affordances* (CA) stand for old elements that could be introduced into new technologies user interfaces with the aim of improving the recognition of the new functions and functionalities and reducing the barriers in the new technology access, mainly for non-expert users [14]. Hence to provide a value for the driver through the HMI in-vehicle design, it is necessary to make HMI becoming an integral part of driver’s life, taking advantage of CA.

This consideration is really important for the EV domain: the user interface bridges the gap of acceptance of the EV and it enables the driver to operate the powertrain. HMI cannot be viewed merely as a frame for gradual evolutionary innovations: HMI design process must be revisited in order to perform its indispensable role in future EVs.

Continuity affordance for the HMI design for EVs

Within the research work done in the RESOLVE project, it was possible to identify the features users desire for the in-vehicle equipment and HMI of ELVs. This activity was carried out by surveys and literature analysis. Identified features are listed below:

- Control of functions by driver/passenger.
- Display information or entertainment (e.g. displays / LCD screens).
- Air flow to driver, passengers and windows and automatic air conditioning status.
- Additional switches for more and more functions (e.g. audio controls in steering wheel).
- Service interval indicator.
- Smart key or card.
- Navigation system.
- Park distance control
- Multi-function steering wheel with cruise control.

Starting from the analysis of the above-mentioned features, three interesting continuity affordances were identified for the HMI design for EVs:

1. **Extra-functional properties.** Some examples of extra-functional properties includes timing

properties and quality attributes like performance, resources, reliability, security, ease of use, real time response, robustness, service capacity, throughput, bandwidth, space requirements, adaptability, precision and accuracy [17].

2. **Plug&Play capabilities.** New functions, sensors, actuators, and other components can be easily integrated in vehicle if platform supports Plug&Play. That would allow the use of nomadic devices such as smartphones or tablets. The Plug&Play concept will allow customers to change and personalize vehicle. Furthermore, these changes will not be limited to changes of the infotainment domain, but of all other domains as well [2].
3. **Seamless reconfigurability.** HMI both for Plug&Play mechanism and resident applications needs to be reconfigurable according to different criteria (e.g. user's preference, context or risk level). Reconfiguration can be triggered by the addition or removal of application components, the addition or removal of resources or component failures, detected driving and driver's conditions. In addition, this mechanism can be used to improve the distribution of workload [2].

A strategy for the design of EV HMI

The HMI strategy defined within RESOLVE project that allows to identify problems and needs concerns firstly the *information delivery mode*, the *engagement modality* and the *target display*.

About the *information delivery mode* the following options can be considered.

- **Always present:** it means information shall be always present on the target display.
- **On demand:** it means user can retrieve information interacting with the HMI controls.
- **Pop-up first, then on demand:** it means an event triggers information that is delivered as a pop-up on the target display and then, if information is still valid, user can retrieve it interacting with the HMI controls.
- **Suitable to be always present:** it means that, as default, information can be retrieved by interacting with the HMI controls, but user has the possibility, through personal settings menu, to set it as "always present".
- **Interaction modality:** it refers to information delivery channel (i.e. visual, acoustic, haptic or a suitable combination).
- **Customization:** it refers to the possibility to customize some features of the information.

About the *function engagement* the following options are considered:

- **Button and knob:** it refers to the possibility to engage or disengage the function by hard controls.
- **Menu controls:** it refers to the possibility to engage or disengage the function through the menu controls that can be hard or soft, according to the selected architecture.

About the target display the following options are considered:

- **Cluster:** it means that information will be delivered on the cluster display.
- **Nomadic Device (ND):** it means that information will be delivered on the display of the connected ND (i.e. smartphone/tablet).

Challenges and opportunities in the HMI design for EV

Starting from the aforementioned features, it is possible to draw a table, where intersecting HMI functions, the HMI strategy is found out, in terms of what to deliver, where and how. An example is shown in table 1. Arranging all the elements of the HMI strategy in a table, and filling it following the project requirements, one gets a complete overview of the HMI features and main requirements, as table 1 shows for the “range estimation” function.

Table 1 Example of HMI strategy table (source: RESOLVE project).

	Delivery modes					
Smart range management	Always present	On demand	Pop-up first, then on demand	Suitable to be always present	Interaction modality	Customization
Range estimation	x				Visual + acoustic warning (i.e. limited range)	Threshold for the acoustic warning; warning volume
		Engagement		Display		
		Button and knob	Menu controls	Cluster	ND	
		NA	NA		x	

Once the overall HMI strategy has been defined, it must be matched with the condition of use, that essentially are the project scenarios. For the electric vehicles domain, three main scenarios were identified:

1. Pre-route (including off-vehicle).
2. On-route (diagnostics, critical events).
3. Post-route (including statistics and learning).

That said, the HMI strategies are considered at this stage of the design process as HMI perspectives:

1. Strategic (route-level).
2. Tactic (4-5 km range).
3. Imminent (contingent).

The analysis of scenarios in each HMI perspective leads to the definition of a two-dimension matrix (shown in table 2) that allow to identify the most relevant use-cases.

Table 2 Structure of the use-case matrix (Source: RESOLVE project).

		Scenario		
		Pre-route	On-route	Post-route
HMI perspective	Strategic (route-level)			
	Tactic (4-5 km range)			
	Imminent (contingent)			

In each scenario some enabling conditions can be added (e.g. engine off + cluster on + ND on; engine on “v = 0” + cluster on + ND off; engine on “v = 0” + cluster on + ND on). The aim of this table is to map the information that will be provided to driver with the different conditions of use and HMI perspectives in order to give to him/her only the necessary and most suitable information for each condition of use. The use-case matrix was created within the RESOLVE project as a concrete support for the iterative design and development of HMI, and it can be modified and enriched during the entire duration of project. Next steps in the project foresee the definition of two different concepts of HMI and related architectures for the demonstrator vehicles, using the strategy explained in this paper. Then a cost analysis will be performed on both the HMI concepts, and the results will lead next decisions on final implementation.

Conclusions

To encourage car drivers to use ELVs for their commuting needs, ELVs need to move closer to what car drivers expect from their mobility solutions by enhancing the driver’s user experience.

In this scenario, the RESOLVE project aims at developing a range of cost-effective, energy efficient and comfortable ELVs, in order to entice ICE car drivers to switch from cars to ELVs for their daily urban commutes. Further aspects as advancements in the handling and stability of ELVs together with improving the user interface that will assuage range anxiety and other driver concerns, such as safety and comfort are investigated too.

Concerning the HMI, it should provide drivers with advice on their driving style on the optimal usage of ELVs. It should give feedback on driver behaviour, such as how drivers have to behave to recuperate the most energy for regenerative braking and how to optimise the active safety systems. For these reasons, the design of the HMI solutions started since the very beginning of project because it is considered as a key measure to achieve project objectives, and turn ELVs into a mass-market product.

As well as technology changed the vehicle cockpit, the telematics revolution of the past decade has generated the possibility for a vehicle to extend the digital information clustering, integrating nomadic devices, smartphones, and tablets empowering in this way the extent of the in-vehicle functions. Moreover last achievements in transport technology allow vehicles to communicate with the road infrastructure and other vehicles in order to increase driver safety, decrease road congestion and

Challenges and opportunities in the HMI design for EV

improve fuel economy and the overall transportation system efficiency.

It is a matter of fact that EVs face the user lack of confidence and trust both, together with the unfamiliarity with a wide range of new functions, as the range management, charging procedures, recharging duration, very low noise, strong acceleration and limited space or a new driving style. In order to assure a positive e rewarding driving experience and make user appreciate EV special driving qualities, the HMI design play a crucial role, together with the development of an effective energy management assistant, able to support user in minimizing energy consumption during regular vehicle use and to be aware of availability and limitations of power. Other HMI-based key functionalities that should be included are trip planner (allowing e.g. the alteration of plans), adaptive and context-aware routing of available energy and self-diagnosis function. Regarding the diagnostic and predictive capabilities of vehicle, useful applications are about battery ageing, state and failure prediction and the management demand and availability of energy.

In order to properly integrate all these functions in the vehicle cockpit, both on the vehicle cluster and on the nomadic devices, and to address the special needs of inexperienced drivers, the introduction of the familiarity concept and continuity affordance could represent a relevant benefit for the HMI design strategy. Keeping them in mind, it is possible to easily draw the global HMI strategy for an EV following the methodology proposed in this paper that supports the designer in identifying all the HMI features that fulfil the project requirements. Then starting from the global HMI strategy it is possible to identify the most relevant use-cases, using the use-case matrix.

Acknowledgment

This research has been performed with support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653511.

References

1. Bish, J. R., & Tietmeyer, G. P. (1983). Electric vehicle field test experience. *Vehicular Technology, IEEE Transactions on*, 32(1), 81-89.
2. Buckl, C., Camek, A., Kainz, G., Simon, C., Mercep, L., Stähle, H., & Knoll, A. (2012, March). The software car: Building ICT architectures for future electric vehicles. In *Electric Vehicle Conference (IEVC), 2012 IEEE International* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
3. Bühler, F., Franke, T., & Krems, J. F. (2011). Usage patterns of electric vehicles as a reliable indicator for acceptance? Findings from a German field study. In *Transportation Research Board 90th Annual Meeting* (No. 11-0227).
4. Calefato, C., Frumento, E., Milani, M., & Montanari, R. (2010, May). Seeing the self in the washing machine: the deep affordance of 2.0 philosophy in the household appliance domain. In *AVI* (p. 405).
5. Calefato C., Landini E., Berzi L. (2015), "Far far away: driving HMI requirements towards the comfortable range in Electric Vehicles", in *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Energy Management, Prediction and Big Data Elaboration (EMENDER 2015)*, available at: <http://ct3.ijs.si/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/EMENDER-publications.rar>.
6. Capros, P., Tasios, N., De Vita, A., Mantzos, L., & Paroussos, L. (2012). Transformations of the energy system in the context of the decarbonisation of the EU economy in the time horizon to 2050. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 1(2), 85-96.
7. Cocron, P., Bühler, F., Neumann, I., Franke, T., Krems, J. F., Schwalm, M., & Keinath, A. (2011). Methods of evaluating electric vehicles from a user's perspective—the MINI E field trial in Berlin. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 5(2), 127-133.
8. Dargay, J., Gately, D., & Sommer, M. (2007). Vehicle ownership and income growth, worldwide: 1960-2030. *The Energy Journal*, 143-170.
9. Endeman, Gertjan (2007) *The design of a user-interface for the powertrain of a car in the future, ...in order to improve the acceptance of this powertrain*, available at <http://essay.utwente.nl/842/>
10. European Commission (2013). *Regulation (Eu) No 168/2013 of the European Parliament and of The Council* , available at:

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013R0168>, consulted on the 19th of February 2016.

11. Franke, T., Neumann, I., Bühler, F., Cocron, P., & Krems, J. F. (2012). Experiencing range in an electric vehicle: Understanding psychological barriers. *Applied Psychology*, 61(3), 368-391.
12. Gibson, J.J. (1979) *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*, Hillsdale, NJ.: Lawrence Erlbaum.
13. Man, W. Y., Bie, J., & van Arem, B. (2012). User Needs in Green ITS: Results of a Questionnaire Survey and Proposal for Green ITS Design. *International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research*, 10(2), 47-55.
14. Montanari, R., Gallenca, G., & Marzani, S. (2007). In Back to the future: Continuity Affordances in interactive TV. In the Proceedings of CHI2007 workshop - Supporting non-professional users in the new media landscape - San Jose, April 29th 2007.
15. Norman, D. (1988) *The Psychology of Everyday Things*, New York: Basic Books.
16. Patil, P. G. (1990). Prospects for electric vehicles. *Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine, IEEE*, 5(12), 15-19.
17. Shaw, M., & Garlan, D. (1995). Formulations and formalisms in software architecture. In *Computer Science Today* (pp. 307-323). Springer Berlin Heidelberg
18. Skinner, I., van Essen, H., Smokers, R., & Hill, N. (2010). Towards the decarbonisation of EU's transport sector by 2050. *Komisja Europejska, Bruksela*.
19. Strömberg, H., Andersson, P., Almgren, S., Ericsson, J., Karlsson, M., & Nåbo, A. (2011, November). Driver interfaces for electric vehicles. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Automotive User Interfaces and Interactive Vehicular Applications* (pp. 177-184). ACM.
20. Struben, J. and Sterman, J.D. (2006) *Transition Challenges for Alternative Fuel Vehicle and Transportation Systems*, MIT Sloan School of Management, Engineering System Division, ESD-WP-2006-06, Downloaded from <http://esd.mit.edu/staging//wps/esd-wp-2006-06.pdf> on 30 August.
21. Turrentine, T., Garas, D., Lentz, A., & Woodjack, J. (2011). The UC davis MINI E consumer study. *Institute of Transportation Studies, University of California, UC Davis Institute of Transportation Studies Research Report*, 5.